

Results of DC and attitudes towards DTs analyses for the total sample by gender.

Items	D1	D2	Girls		Boys		t	p	Cohen's D
			Mean	SD	Mean	SD			
Total DC			3.69	.60	3.72	.64	-1.276	.101	.623
CD01. Understanding where to start an exercise in class, going beyond what I'm told	.534		3.6	1.032	3.64	1.006	-.96	.169	1.02
CD02. Finding the complete version of a document that I only know the title of	.581		3.56	1.149	3.61	1.107	-1.215	.112	1.129
CD03. Confirming a fact I found in Wikipedia but I'm not sure about	.546		3.64	1.191	3.64	1.132	-.037	.485	1.163
CD04. Saving the links used during a project in an organized manner	.58		4.06	1.138	3.79	1.209	6.626	<.001	1.173
CD05. Making digital concept maps before writing	.58		3.21	1.291	2.95	1.262	5.718	<.001	1.277
CD06. Connecting to the most secure available Wi Fi network	.421		4.1	1.162	4.3	1.067	-4.955	<.001	1.117
CD07. Digitize a document with good resolution	.582		3.63	1.234	3.68	1.262	-1.262	.104	1.248
CD08. Converting a text file into a PDF	.536		4.06	1.277	4.12	1.239	-1.281	.1	1.259
CD09. Sending an email with a blind carbon copy	.363		2.67	1.557	2.93	1.559	-4.892	<.001	1.558
CD10. Designing a new template for a slide presentation	.538		4.07	1.28	3.97	1.281	2.263	.012	1.281
CD11. Summarizing the main idea of a documentary in a 280-character tweet	.642		3.53	1.298	3.45	1.346	1.836	.033	1.322
CD12. Determining whether presentations given by classmates are too simple	.527		4.22	.969	4.05	1.055	4.794	<.001	1.012
CD13. Realizing when a multimedia message is misleading	.473		3.95	1.105	4.1	1.042	-3.904	<.001	1.075
CD14. Choosing the best option (traditional camera, cell phone camera, etc.) for filming a video	.476		4.35	.941	4.32	.96	.699	.242	.951
CD15. Preparing my video CV	.469		2.67	1.441	2.78	1.436	-2.366	.009	1.439
CD16. Sending a 2GB video to friends over the internet	.527		3.56	1.438	3.85	1.363	-5.948	<.001	1.402
CD17. Holding a video conference with three or more friends	.343		4.83	.604	4.73	.739	4.094	<.001	.673
CD18. Publishing digital content with a Creative Commons licence	.325		2.14	1.308	2.33	1.376	-4.057	<.001	1.341
CD19. Working collaboratively on a shared document in the cloud	.582		3.92	1.405	4.11	1.248	-4.05	<.001	1.331
ATTITUDE			3.89	.71	3.94	.73	-1.587	.056	.723
ACT01. I find them easy to use.	.431		4.27	.951	4.32	.926	-1.53	.063	.939
ACT02. I enjoy using them.	.607		4.21	1.002	4.28	.987	-1.871	.031	.995
ACT03. They help me learn independently.	.545		4.14	.983	4.11	.997	.75	.227	.99
ACT04. They make it easier for me to communicate with my classmates and teachers.	.452		4.53	.866	4.42	.96	3.433	<.001	.913
ACT05. I learn better when I use them.	.765		3.77	1.104	3.83	1.122	-1.58	.057	1.113
ACT06. Using them increases my motivation.	.817		3.63	1.197	3.73	1.213	-2.305	.011	1.205
ACT07. Using them enhances my creativity.	.728		3.69	1.183	3.81	1.161	-2.758	.003	1.172
ACT08. Using them enhances my writing.	.545		3.15	1.383	3.2	1.434	-.838	.201	1.408
ACT09. We should learn more about them in school.	.647		3.65	1.179	3.72	1.195	-1.652	.049	1.187

Note: D1: Factor weight of each item for DC; D2: Factor weight of each item for attitude towards DTs; SD: Standard deviation

Results of DC and attitude towards DTs analyses for 2nd year of ESO by gender.

Items	Girls		Boys		t	p	Cohen's D
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD			
Total DC	3.63	.595	3.64	.673	-.373	0.354	.636
CD01. Understanding where to start an exercise in class, going beyond what I'm told	3.64	1.068	3.58	1.062	.964	.168	1.065
CD02. Finding the complete version of a document that I only know the title of	3.42	1.16	3.51	1.121	-1.543	.062	1.141
CD03. Confirming a fact I found in Wikipedia but I'm not sure about	3.52	1.223	3.54	1.155	-.42	.337	1.189
CD04. Saving the links used during a project in an organized manner	4	1.196	3.72	1.222	4.473	<.001	1.209
CD05. Making digital concept maps before writing	3.15	1.299	2.88	1.286	4.159	<.001	1.292
CD06. Connecting to the most secure available Wi Fi network	4.15	1.138	4.33	1.07	-3.152	<.001	1.104
CD07. Digitize a document with good resolution	3.59	1.216	3.62	1.287	-.382	.351	1.253
CD08. Converting a text file into a PDF	3.89	1.354	3.96	1.317	-1.082	.14	1.335
CD09. Sending an email with a blind carbon copy	2.73	1.573	2.96	1.556	-2.913	.002	1.564
CD10. Designing a new template for a slide presentation	4.03	1.279	3.9	1.328	1.851	.032	1.304
CD11. Summarizing the main idea of a documentary in a 280-character tweet	3.27	1.36	3.23	1.379	.568	.285	1.37
CD12. Determining whether presentations given by classmates are too simple	4.18	1.006	3.98	1.09	3.68	<.001	1.049
CD13. Realizing when a multimedia message is misleading	3.95	1.131	4.07	1.074	-2.085	.019	1.102
CD14. Choosing the best option (traditional camera, cell phone camera, etc.) for filming a video	4.37	.907	4.32	.964	.979	.164	.936
CD15. Preparing my video CV	2.62	1.47	2.67	1.435	-.545	.293	1.452
CD16. Sending a 2GB video to friends over the internet	3.5	1.453	3.72	1.437	-2.841	.002	1.445
CD17. Holding a video conference with three or more friends	4.79	.705	4.68	.824	2.756	.003	.768
CD18. Publishing digital content with a Creative Commons licence	2.15	1.321	2.35	1.396	-2.917	.002	1.36
CD19. Working collaboratively on a shared document in the cloud	3.71	1.457	3.92	1.346	-2.913	.002	1.401
ATTITUDE	3.94	.682	3.94	.734	-.111	.456	.709
ACT01. I find them easy to use.	4.34	.945	4.32	.954	.544	.293	.95
ACT02. I enjoy using them.	4.3	.975	4.31	1.013	-.229	.41	.994
ACT03. They help me learn independently.	4.13	.99	4.06	1.029	1.265	.103	1.01
ACT04. They make it easier for me to communicate with my classmates and teachers.	4.56	.862	4.44	.958	2.501	.006	.912
ACT05. I learn better when I use them.	3.85	1.057	3.8	1.143	.867	.193	1.102
ACT06. Using them increases my motivation.	3.74	1.187	3.81	1.228	-1.126	.13	1.208
ACT07. Using them enhances my creativity.	3.77	1.191	3.89	1.136	-2.119	.017	1.164
ACT08. Using them enhances my writing.	3.15	1.409	3.22	1.451	-.915	.18	1.431
ACT09. We should learn more about them in school.	3.64	1.179	3.66	1.234	-.309	.379	1.207

Note: SD: Standard deviation

Results of DC and attitude towards DTs analyses for 4th year of ESO by gender.

Items	Girls		Boys		t	p	Cohen's d
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD			
Total DC	3.71	.619	3.75	.619	-1.181	.119	.619
CD01. Understanding where to start an exercise in class, going beyond what I'm told	3.6	1.011	3.69	.956	-1.627	.052	.985
CD02. Finding the complete version of a document that I only know the title of	3.63	1.152	3.65	1.105	-.374	0.354	1.13
CD03. Confirming a fact I found in Wikipedia but I'm not sure about	3.72	1.156	3.7	1.104	.334	.369	1.132
CD04. Saving the links used during a project in an organized manner	4.1	1.112	3.83	1.196	4.316	<.001	1.153
CD05. Making digital concept maps before writing	3.28	1.274	2.96	1.232	4.693	<.001	1.254
CD06. Connecting to the most secure available Wi Fi network	4.1	1.184	4.3	1.056	-3.195	<.001	1.125
CD07. Digitize a document with good resolution	3.6	1.265	3.68	1.249	-1.155	.124	1.258
CD08. Converting a text file into a PDF	4.13	1.228	4.17	1.196	-.565	.286	1.213
CD09. Sending an email with a blind carbon copy	2.61	1.538	2.89	1.554	-3.369	<.001	1.546
CD10. Designing a new template for a slide presentation	4.1	1.287	4.01	1.245	1.278	.101	1.267
CD11. Summarizing the main idea of a documentary in a 280-character tweet	3.65	1.248	3.56	1.312	1.413	.079	1.279
CD12. Determining whether presentations given by classmates are too simple	4.23	.949	4.06	1.054	3.206	<.001	1
CD13. Realizing when a multimedia message is misleading	3.93	1.097	4.11	1.02	-3.005	.001	1.061
CD14. Choosing the best option (traditional camera, cell phone camera, etc.) for filming a video	4.31	.983	4.36	.949	-.892	.186	.967
CD15. Preparing my video CV	2.74	1.451	2.85	1.433	-1.438	.075	1.443
CD16. Sending a 2GB video to friends over the internet	3.55	1.441	3.98	1.28	-5.731	<.001	1.366
CD17. Holding a video conference with three or more friends	4.84	.552	4.77	.654	2.074	.019	.603
CD18. Publishing digital content with a Creative Commons licence	2.13	1.268	2.27	1.332	-1.912	.028	1.299
CD19. Working collaboratively on a shared document in the cloud	3.97	1.399	4.22	1.167	-3.547	<.001	1.294
ATTITUDE	3.86	.736	3.93	.728	-1.792	.037	.733
ACT01. I find them easy to use.	4.2	.99	4.32	.916	-2.419	.008	.956
ACT02. I enjoy using them.	4.12	1.039	4.26	.969	-2.423	.008	1.006
ACT03. They help me learn independently.	4.11	1.006	4.14	.977	-.517	.303	.992
ACT04. They make it easier for me to communicate with my classmates and teachers.	4.52	.872	4.44	.933	1.7	.045	.901
ACT05. I learn better when I use them.	3.73	1.121	3.9	1.089	-2.787	.003	1.106
ACT06. Using them increases my motivation.	3.62	1.187	3.7	1.194	-1.367	.086	1.191
ACT07. Using them enhances my creativity.	3.67	1.178	3.73	1.163	-.988	.162	1.171
ACT08. Using them enhances my writing.	3.2	1.363	3.16	1.423	.463	.322	1.392
ACT09. We should learn more about them in school.	3.64	1.198	3.8	1.152	-2.439	.007	1.176

Note: SD Standard deviation

Results of DC and attitude towards DTs analyses for 2nd year of upper secondary by gender.

Items	Girls		Boys		t	p	Cohen's D
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD			
Total DC	3.80	.535	3.89	.573	-1.769	.039	.552
CD01. Understanding where to start an exercise in class, going beyond what I'm told	3.49	.976	3.67	.933	-1.875	.031	.957
CD02. Finding the complete version of a document that I only know the title of	3.84	1.031	3.92	.991	-.732	.232	1.014
CD03. Confirming a fact I found in Wikipedia but I'm not sure about	3.76	1.163	3.81	1.103	-.492	.312	1.137
CD04. Saving the links used during a project in an organized manner	4.15	1.019	3.94	1.185	1.87	.031	1.095
CD05. Making digital concept maps before writing	3.14	1.308	3.23	1.232	-.659	.255	1.275
CD06. Connecting to the most secure available Wi Fi network	3.98	1.164	4.18	1.091	-1.819	.035	1.132
CD07. Digitizing a document with good resolution	3.82	1.182	3.96	1.169	-1.234	.109	1.176
CD08. Converting a text file into a PDF	4.41	1.071	4.6	.856	-1.937	.027	.982
CD09. Sending an email with a blind carbon copy	2.64	1.565	2.95	1.594	-1.96	.025	1.578
CD10. Designing a new template for a slide presentation	4.13	1.26	4.11	1.195	.162	.436	1.232
CD11. Summarizing the main idea of a documentary in a 280-character tweet	4	1.041	3.97	1.121	.218	.414	1.077
CD12. Determining whether presentations given by classmates are too simple	4.28	.907	4.27	.871	.033	.487	.891
CD13. Realizing when a multimedia message is misleading	4	1.049	4.18	.983	-1.76	.04	1.021
CD14. Choosing the best option (traditional camera, cell phone camera, etc.) for filming a video	4.37	.921	4.19	.979	1.932	.027	.947
CD15. Preparing my video CV	2.57	1.308	3.04	1.41	-3.536	<.001	1.354
CD16. Sending a 2GB video to friends over the internet	3.79	1.368	4	1.282	-1.614	.054	1.331
CD17. Holding a video conference with three or more friends	4.92	.341	4.81	.623	2.278	.012	.486
CD18. Publishing digital content with a Creative Commons licence	2.12	1.387	2.44	1.446	-2.288	.011	1.413
CD19. Working collaboratively on a shared document in the cloud	4.45	1.061	4.52	.918	-.671	.251	1.001
ATTITUDE	3.82	.732	3.87	.749	-.635	.263	.740
ACT01. I find them easy to use.	4.28	.827	4.35	.842	-.849	.198	.834
ACT02. I enjoy using them.	4.21	.955	4.22	.941	-.075	.47	.949
ACT03. They help me learn independently.	4.23	.884	4.19	.928	.362	.359	.904
ACT04. They make it easier for me to communicate with my classmates and teachers.	4.48	.861	4.28	1.053	2.035	.021	.95
ACT05. I learn better when I use them.	3.6	1.179	3.68	1.141	-.697	.243	1.162
ACT06. Using them increases my motivation.	3.36	1.219	3.51	1.189	-1.228	.11	1.206
ACT07. Using them enhances my creativity.	3.54	1.156	3.72	1.238	-1.474	.071	1.193
ACT08. Using them enhances my writing.	3.02	1.362	3.21	1.405	-1.335	.091	1.381
ACT09. We should learn more about them in school.	3.73	1.122	3.71	1.17	.159	.437	1.144

Note: SD: Standard deviation